

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

SPOCK1

(SPARC (osteonectin), cwcv and kazal like domains proteoglycan 1)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	6695 / Q08629
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD, AMP-AD
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Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
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Bioinformatic analysis: Target source & hypothesis

Protein constructs & expression methods: SPOCK1_23-439_HisN_AviC. Baculovirus expression for structure determination.

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.93 (rank #494, 98th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.46 out of 5 (rank #2148, 91.4th percentile). The individual score components include 1.62 of 3 for genetics, and 1.84 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of SPOCK1 protein is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. SPOCK1 is annotated to GO terms from the Synapse, Structural Stabilization, Myelination and Metal Binding and Homeostasis domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of

expression. The expression of SPOCK1 is confidently detected in oligodendrocytes, oligodendrocyte precursor cells (OPC), astrocytes, and both excitatory and inhibitory neuron sub-types within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

The SPOCK1 project is promoted by the discovery that SPOCK1 is a hub protein in module 42 (M42), which is linked with AD pathological progression and cognitive decline in AD patients (1). While there are many studies linking SPOCK1 to neurodevelopment, its role in neurodegenerative sequelae is completely unexplored. The development of this target enablement package (TEP) includes a characterization of

available antibodies, purified protein, and a bioinformatics characterization of the AD risk association and the expression patterns for SPOCK1. We hope this will help ease the barrier to future investigations into the role of SPOCK1 in AD.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

The SPOCK1 gene encodes the Testican-1 (TICN-1) protein, comprised of 439 amino acids, featuring various domains structural domains such as Kazal-like, EF hand extracellular calcium binding, and a thyroglobulin type-1 domain (2) (UniProt: Q08629). SPOCK1 is a proteoglycan predominantly expressed in the brain (3). Various members of the SPOCK family exhibit distinct expression patterns during development, with SPOCK1 expressed in both early development, in periods associated with neurogenesis, and in later adult mouse brain, potentially facilitating synaptic wiring and synaptic field mapping into adulthood within the mouse brain (3). Disruption of other SPOCK family members' function leads to anomalies in neuronal connectivity, affecting the size and degree of myelination within the corpus callosum (4). SPOCK1's role in development may have its molecular roots in the regulation of different classes of cellular proteases, with evidence in support of inhibitory roles with both membrane type matrix metalloproteases (5) and lysosomal cathepsins (6, 7). This may also have a role in regulating cellular adhesion, as elevated levels of SPOCK1 inhibit attachment of N2a cells (8) and may also contribute to the increase in metastatic potential of astroglomas (9, 10). Traumatic injury to the brain is also associated with changes in SPOCK1 expression levels, in which regions surrounding the damage neural tissue show elevated SPOCK1 expression adjacent to reactive astrocytes, potentially facilitating axonal regeneration through the damaged tissue (11). The role of SPOCK1 in neurodevelopment is supported by mutations in the SPOCK1 gene being associated with brain abnormalities including microencephaly and corpus callosum formation deficits (12). In addition to SPOCK1's role in neuronal development, it appears to play a role in formation of the blood brain barrier, potentially through the regulation of astrocytic encapsulation of the neurovasculature or the regulation of the endothelial cells in the blood vessels, as mutant SPOCK1 decreases the viability of the blood-brain-barrier (BBB) and an allelic rescue with wild-type SPOCK1 promotes a restoration of the BBB through a restoration of normal extracellular matrix function (13).

The role of SPOCK1 in neurobiology suggests a developmental role that perseveres into adulthood; however, that does not explain its potential role in AD. In recent work by our group, using deep brain proteomic methods, SPOCK1 was identified as a core hub protein in a proteomic module associated with AD pathogenesis and clinical cognitive decline [module 42 (M42)] (1). M42 playing a functional role in AD progression is supported by the presence of APP and APOE membership in this 32 protein module. Additionally, there is evidence that APP may regulate the subcellular sorting of SPOCK1 localization and accumulation, suggesting a potential mechanistic interaction between these two genes (14). The biological mechanism linking SPOCK1 with other M42 proteins is yet to be elucidated but given the regulation of metalloproteinase function by SPOCK1, the high frequency of secretion among M42 proteins, further investigation into SPOCK1's role is justified. We hope that resources developed in this project will aid in exploring SPOCK1's biological role in AD.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Protein Constructs

1. SPOCK1_23-439_HisN_AviC. Baculovirus expression for structure determination.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further investigation of the role of SPOCK1 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Proteins Expression and Purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

References

1. Johnson ECB, Carter EK, Dammer EB, Duong DM, Gerasimov ES, Liu Y, et al. Large-scale deep multi-layer analysis of Alzheimer's disease brain reveals strong proteomic disease-related changes not observed at the RNA level. *Nat Neurosci*. 2022;25(2):213-25.
2. Vannahme C, Schubel S, Herud M, Gosling S, Hulsmann H, Paulsson M, et al. Molecular cloning of testican-2: defining a novel calcium-binding proteoglycan family expressed in brain. *J Neurochem*. 1999;73(1):12-20.
3. Charbonnier F, Chanoine C, Cifuentes-Diaz C, Gallien CL, Rieger F, Alliel PM, Perin JP. Expression of the proteoglycan SPOCK during mouse embryo development. *Mech Dev*. 2000;90(2):317-21.
4. Yamamoto A, Uchiyama K, Nara T, Nishimura N, Hayasaka M, Hanaoka K, Yamamoto T. Structural abnormalities of corpus callosum and cortical axonal tracts accompanied by decreased anxiety-like behavior and lowered sociability in spock3- mutant mice. *Dev Neurosci*. 2014;36(5):381-95.
5. Nakada M, Yamada A, Takino T, Miyamori H, Takahashi T, Yamashita J, Sato H. Suppression of membrane-type 1 matrix metalloproteinase (MMP)-mediated MMP-2 activation and tumor invasion by testican 3 and its splicing variant gene product, N-Tes. *Cancer Res*. 2001;61(24):8896-902.
6. Bocock JP, Edgell CJ, Marr HS, Erickson AH. Human proteoglycan testican-1 inhibits the lysosomal cysteine protease cathepsin L. *Eur J Biochem*. 2003;270(19):4008-15.
7. Edgell CJ, BaSalamah MA, Marr HS. Testican-1: a differentially expressed proteoglycan with protease inhibiting activities. *Int Rev Cytol*. 2004;236:101-22.
8. Marr HS, Edgell CJ. Testican-1 inhibits attachment of Neuro-2a cells. *Matrix Biol*. 2003;22(3):259-66.
9. Colin C, Baeza N, Bartoli C, Fina F, Eudes N, Nanni I, et al. Identification of genes differentially expressed in glioblastoma versus pilocytic astrocytoma using Suppression Subtractive Hybridization. *Oncogene*. 2006;25(19):2818-26.
10. Yu F, Li G, Gao J, Sun Y, Liu P, Gao H, et al. SPOCK1 is upregulated in recurrent glioblastoma and contributes to metastasis and Temozolomide resistance. *Cell Prolif*. 2016;49(2):195-206.
11. Iseki K, Hagino S, Zhang Y, Mori T, Sato N, Yokoya S, et al. Altered expression pattern of testican-1 mRNA after brain injury. *Biomed Res*. 2011;32(6):373-8.
12. Dhamija R, Graham JM, Jr., Smaoui N, Thorland E, Kirmani S. Novel de novo SPOCK1 mutation in a proband with developmental delay, microcephaly and agenesis of corpus callosum. *Eur J Med Genet*. 2014;57(4):181-4.
13. O'Brown NM, Patel NB, Hartmann U, Klein AM, Gu C, Megason SG. The secreted neuronal signal Spock1 promotes blood-brain barrier development. *Dev Cell*. 2023;58(17):1534-47 e6.

14. Barrera-Ocampo A, Arlt S, Matschke J, Hartmann U, Puig B, Ferrer I, et al. Amyloid-beta Precursor Protein Modulates the Sorting of Testican-1 and Contributes to Its Accumulation in Brain Tissue and Cerebrospinal Fluid from Patients with Alzheimer Disease. *J Neuropathol Exp Neurol*. 2016;75(9):903-16.

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